

The Role of Ethical Leadership in Reducing Counterproductive Work Behavior: A Study in the Egyptian Context

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to identify the role of Ethical Leadership (EL) in reducing Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt. The research community is composed of all employees of Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt. Due to the time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted the sampling method to collect the necessary data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) the results support the view that EL (fairness, integrity, role clarification, power-sharing, people-orientation, and ethical guidance) is related to CWB (theft, withdrawal, sabotage, kickbacks/corruption, and misuse of time and resources) at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt, (2) the relationship between EL and CWB in the organization is presented. The palliative role that EL can play in this relationship has been identified, (3) the present study emphasized the inverse relationship between EL and CWB in the organization. This requires the need for the advancement of educational and religious institutions to improve the ethics of leadership in general and work ethics in particular, (4) the study found that the most influential dimensions of EL in CWB are, respectively, ethical orientation, individual orientation, fairness, integrity, role clarification, and power-sharing, (5) the present study emphasized the relationship between EL and CWB within the organization. This requires the need to develop the principle of self-control among employees in the organization. The development of work love and the spirit of the loyalty of employees in order to reduce the CWB within the organization.

The study referred to a number of recommendations, the most important of which are: (1) managers at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt can help their employees, through training interventions, to develop their EL, (2) Pharmaceutical companies must select ethical leaders, work for their development, and maintain their presence within organizations, (3) embody the principles of EL of administrative leaders to be more immersed in organizational culture and be a feature of organizational culture, (4) the need to pay attention to the mechanisms of social exchange through which to increase the impact of EL on the engagement of work and emotional commitment, (5) raising awareness and interest in the development of EL practices of leaders by subjecting them to training courses in this field, (6) the need to develop relations of social exchange between leaders and subordinates in the organizations, and attention to the development of moral climate, and the behavior of EL, (7) developing trust relationships between the leader and subordinates, determining the importance of the identity of the leader and the extent of his representation of the organization, (8) increasing the awareness of administrative leaders about the dimensions of integrity, people orientation, and power sharing, because of its positive impact on the behavior of workers, (9) the need for organizations to pay attention to good human resources practices to increase the level of EL.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Counterproductive Work Behavior

1. Introduction

Ethical Leadership (EL) is a very important topic. Organizations need leaders who act ethically, develop ethical behavior, encourage employees to deal with such behavior in their daily work, as well as to prevent unethical behaviors and practices. Business ethics is behavior that is consistent with the principles and standards of business practices agreed on by the community (Trevino & Nelson, 2011).

Ethical behavior is a shared responsibility of all parties involved with the organization. Ethical leaders also determine the nature of decisions that are made, as well as the role that ethics plays in making these decisions (Stouten, et al., 2012).

Organizations must select ethical leaders, work for their development, and maintain their presence within organizations (Brown & Trevino, 2006).

Many researchers have been interested in studying the outcome of EL and doing research that helps improve their performance (Brown & Trevino, 2006; 2014; Choi, et al., 2015).

Many researchers have studied the variables associated with EL (De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008).

There is still a need for researchers to test how EL affects the behavior of employees. Despite increasing evidence linking EL to subordinate behavior, more research is needed in this area (Dajani, 2015; Den Hartog & Belschak. 2012; Khuong & Dung, 2015; Neves & Story. 2015).

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In spite of research and discussion on the subject of EL, it remains one of the topics that need to conduct research and associated studies (Brown & Trevino, 2006).

Until very recently, little has been done to develop a clear methodology for EL that contributes to the examination of EL theory in terms of roots, origins, and results (Brown, et al., 2005).

At the time of the corporate scandals and ethical lapses, the public and their stakeholders ask themselves the following key question: Who are the leaders of these organizations? Are they moral? Only in recent years have leaders and researchers begun to turn their attention to leadership ethics (Trevino & Brown, 2005). Concern for ethical consciousness began at a time when the legitimacy of leadership became questionable when public confidence in the leadership of organizations became too low (Fulmer, 2005).

In recent years, deviant work behavior has gained increasing attention among organized researchers. This concern is due to the increasing prevalence of these behaviors in the workplace as well as the enormous costs associated with the practice (Fox et al., 2001; Peterson, 2002). Deviant work behavior includes many practices such as theft, absenteeism, violence, incidents of sabotage, fraud, withholding of effort and aggressive behavior, bad work and misuse of time and resources, bribery and forgery (Ones, 2002; Gruy & Sackett, 2003). Deviant work behavior is the unethical practice of employees (Raelin, 1994). Also, deviant work behavior is the voluntary behavior of employees (Robinson & Bennett, 1995). Deviant work behavior is regulated by organizational aggression (Fox et al., 2001). Deviant work behavior is one that hurts the organization directly by negatively affecting its functions or by harming its staff in a way that reduces their effectiveness (Fox et al., 2001).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Ethical Leadership

2.1.1. Ethical Leadership Concept

EL is the organization's demonstration of appropriate normative behavior and practical demonstration of such behavior through interpersonal relationships, encouragement of subordinate behavior through two-way communication, and decision-making. In other words, EL is the expression of appropriate norms, principles and values through individual actions and relationships with others, as well as communicating this behavior to subordinates through communication between the parties and decision-making (Brown, et al., 2005).

It should be noted that the majority of descriptive social empirical research on EL focuses on this definition, which emphasizes fair decision-making, demonstration of ethical behavior, listening to workers, and attention to maximizing benefits for them (Eisenbeiss, 2012; Mahembe & Engelbrecht. 2013).

EL directly means leading others in a way that respects their rights and dignity through the social authority of these leaders (Resick et al., 2006).

EL is to provide a moral and ethical model for subordinates, while at the same time striving to increase the profits from their activities, although these activities may harm the values of the society in general (Arenson, 2001).

EL is that leaders conduct ethical behavior when they do what is right, just and morally good, as well as when they provide support to subordinates to increase their moral awareness and achieve moral self (Zhu, 2004).

2.1.2. Ethical Leadership Dimensions

By reviewing the theoretical literature of EL, the researcher found a set of behavioral dimensions of EL in business organizations. One of the most important studies carried out in this area is the Brown et al., 2005, which is based on subsequent studies on EL.

De Hoogh & Den Hartog (2008) distinguished between three main dimensions of EL (equity, clarification of role, power-sharing), which are included in the Brown et al., 2005 study. In addition to these basic dimensions, other dimensions of EL (people orientation, integrity, ethical guidance) are discussed in other studies.

1. Fairness

Fairness is seen as the most important dimension in the conduct of the moral leader, which means that the moral leader behaves with integrity and treats others in an ethical manner. In other words, the leader must make fair choices, be trustworthy, be truthful, do not practice nepotism, and take responsibility for his actions.

2. Role Clarification

Role clarifying means that the leader is transparent and engages in an open communication process with subordinates (Brown et al., 2005).

The process of role clarification is an essential component of EL. The ethical leader clarifies responsibilities. In the light of these clarifications, the subordinates are fully aware of everything exactly what is required of them. Therefore, they look forward to knowing when they reach the required level of performance (De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2009).

Also, subordinates are not worried about any unclear expectations or not knowing how they can contribute to the achievement of the objectives of the organization as a whole. Since all things are clear to them in light of the explanations given to them by their leadership, they need no further clarification except for new objectives in the light of the reviews in the organization (De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2009).

3. Power Sharing

Power Sharing means that a leader allows subordinates to participate in decision-making and to listen to and take care of their ideas. The leader also listens to the voice of subordinates (De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2009).

Power-sharing also means that a leader allows subordinates to participate in controlling the work assigned to them and making them more independent of their leaders (Resick et al, 2006; Brown et al, 2005).

4. People Orientation

People orientation means that the leader has a genuine interest in others and their problems, respect for their interests and support, and as much as possible to meet their needs (Resick et al, 2006).

The ethical leader communicates and clarifies standards regarding the ethical behavior required of individuals. This is through the organization's senior leadership, which clarifies the set of ethical norms and standards, which in turn provide principles and clarifications for ethical behavior (Beu & Buckley, 2001; Trevino, 2003).

Leaders can raise the level of staff with these principles and standards. Therefore, leaders use the power of rewards and sanctions to keep subordinates feel responsible for their actions. Consequently, they bear the reward and punishment that follows these actions (Trevino et al, 2003).

5. Ethical Guidance

Ethical leaders guide their subordinates, help them in the process of setting priorities, and give them their expertise on the ethical problems they face and how to manage them. These behaviors are called ethical guidance, which is specifically aware of the process of communication about ethics, clarification of ethical rules, and rewards and promotion of ethical behavior among subordinates (Brown et al., 2005).

6. Integrity

Integrity is the link between words and deeds, in other words to what extent an individual says what goes with what he or she does (Palanski & Yammarino, 2009).

Leaders who keep their promises and pledges consistently can be trusted by subordinates because their actions and actions are unexpected and unsurprising to subordinates (Simons, 2010).

An ethical leader is the one who keeps his promises, and generally acts in a predictable way. In other words, there is an agreement between what they express and the way they do (Yuki, 2006).

2.2. Counterproductive Work Behavior

2.2.1. Counterproductive Work Behavior Concept

There are three categories of job behavior practiced by employees in the organization in general. They are task behavior, organizational citizenship behavior and CWB (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002).

Task behavior is the behavior that contributes to the core maintenance and conversion activity of the organization such as product making, sale of goods, delivery of services, followers of managers, scheduling (Motowidlo & Schmit, 1999).

Organizational citizenship behavior is voluntary behavior that is not part of the formal incentive system of the Organization and is intended to enhance the Organization's performance and increase its effectiveness and efficiency (Organ, 1990).

CWB is one that hurts the organization either directly by negatively affecting its functions, or by harming its staff in a way that reduces their effectiveness (Fox et al., 2001).

CWB is a voluntary behavior of employees by violating regulatory standards in a way that harms either the organization or its members or both (Robinson & Bennett, 1995).

CWB is the unethical practices of workers, absenteeism, evasion, exaggeration, indifference and immaturity (Raelin, 1994).

CWB is also regulated by organizational aggression (Fox et al., 2001), or dysfunctional (Griffin et al., 1998) or antisocial behavior (Giacalone & Greenberg, 1997).

In recent years, CWB has gained increasing attention among organized researchers, but attention has shifted from studying desired work behaviors to unwanted work behaviors. This concern is due to the increasing prevalence of these behaviors in the workplace as well as the enormous costs associated with the practice (Fox et al., 2001; Peterson, 2002).

CWB includes many practices such as theft, absenteeism, violence, incidents of sabotage, fraud, withholding of effort and aggressive behavior, bad work and misuse of time and resources, bribery and forgery (Ones, 2002; Gruy & Sackett, 2003).

Although many studies address the issue of CWB as having two dimensions: organizational deviation and deviation in interpersonal relationships (Robinson, 1995; Bennett & Robinson, 2000; Hollinger & Clark, 1982), the current research objective will focus only on the first dimension.

2.2.2. Counterproductive Work Behavior Dimensions

There are five dimensions of CWB. They are abuse against others, production deviance, sabotage, theft and withdrawal (Spector et al. 2006).

Abuse against others is a dimension of CWB. It aimed at harming fellow workers and is considered a direct form of aggression (Spector et al. 2006).

The range of abuse at workplace can start from objectionable comments (Cortina & Magley 2003) verbal aggression (Porath & Erez 2009) to stressors like bullying at work (Vickers 2001; Saunders et al. 2007; Monks et al. 2009) and such acts can go on for a longer time period (Ayoko et al. 2003).

If corrective actions are not taken to control this form of CWB, the organization has to ultimately bear its cost (Steffgen 2008) in the form of reduced performance (Altman & Akdere 2008) and increased turnover (Baruch 2005).

Production deviance is another dimension of CWB. It has been thoroughly researched. In this type of CWB, the employee negatively affects organizational efficiency by intentionally hampering quality and quality of work (Hollinger & Clark 1982).

So when an employee purposefully does not perform a task which he was capable of performing, he is indulged in production deviance. This is a serious form of CWB, as an employee who was supposed to facilitate organizational performance is intentionally creating hurdles against its success (Spector et al. 2006).

Sabotage is another dimension of CWB. The employee is engaged in seditious activities and he damages the physical assets in the organization (Chen & Spector 1992).

Despite the fact that productive deviance is a passive and sabotage is an active approach, theoretically both are intertwined (Spector et al. 2006).

Defaming your organization by criticizing it publically also falls under the purview of sabotage (Tucker 1993) while in the new era misuse of information and communication technology against organizational interest is also referred to as sabotage (Weatherbee 2010).

Theft is a dimension of CWB. The employee intends to harm the organization (Niehoff & Paul 2000) intentionally and it can be a form of falsified records, forgery, payroll frauds (Gabbidon et al. 2006) and stealing cash (Schmidtke 2007).

Theft is a problem for all businesses and sectors including the public sector organizations (Saucer 2007).

Theft in organizations is facilitated by employee discontent (Bolin & Heatherly 2001) dissatisfaction (Kulas et al. 2007) and a perception that they will not be caught due to poor control system (Hollinger & Clark 1983).

Since in the USA alone, each year billions of dollars are lost due to employee theft, organizations should focus on controlling theft by formulating the best possible policies and using well planned and well thought out security procedures (Lipman & McGraw 1988).

Similarly when an employee remains absent, takes unauthorized breaks, attends late, leaves early or takes a fake sick leave, the employee is involved in time theft and such behaviors are commonly referred to as withdrawal (Spector et al. 2006; Kulas et al. 2007). Withdrawal has a unique place in the domain of CWB (Marcus & Schuler 2004)

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram shows that there is one independent variable of EL. There is one dependent variable of CWB. It shows the rational link between the two types of observed variables.

EL as measured consists of fairness, integrity, role clarification, power-sharing, people-orientation, and ethical guidance (Brown et al., 2005).

CWB is measured in terms of theft, withdrawal, sabotage, kickbacks/corruption, and misuse of time and resources (Spector et al., 2006).

Figure (1): Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

4. Research Questions

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies. There is a lack in the number of literature review that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between EL and CWB. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted an interview with (30) employees at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt to identify the dimensions of EL and CWB. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the blurred important and the vital role that could be played by EL in affecting CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt. The research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between EL (Fairness) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?
- Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between EL (Role Clarification) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?
- Q3: What is the nature of the relationship between EL (Power Sharing) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?
- Q4: What is the extent of the relationship between EL (People Orientation) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?
- Q5: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?
- Q6: What is the extent of the relationship between EL (Integrity) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between EL and CWB.

- H1: There is no relationship between EL (Fairness) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.
- H2: EL (Role Clarification) has no statistically significant effect on CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.
- H3: There is no relationship between EL (Power Sharing) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

H4: There is no relationship between EL (People Orientation) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

H5: There is no relationship between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

H6: EL (Integrity) has no statistically significant effect on CWB at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

6. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at the Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt. This sector includes five companies. They are Delta for the Pharmaceutical Industry, Egyptian International Pharmaceutical Industries (Eipico), Pharma Sweden, Egypt Otsu, and Egyptian Chemicals and Drugs. This explains why the population of this study includes 4,783 employees. The random sampling was used for collecting the primary data as it was difficult to get all of the items of the research population because of time limitations. The stratified random sample was used while selecting items from the different categories of employees. The following equation determines the sampling size (Daniel, 1999):

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

Accordingly, the sample size has become 356 employees in the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Egyptian Pharmaceutical Companies in Egypt	Employees	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Delta for the Pharmaceutical Industry	1500	31.4%	356X 31.4% = 112
2. Egyptian International Pharmaceutical Industries (Eipico)	1833	38.3%	356X 38.3% = 136
3. Pharma Sweden	850	17.8%	356 17.8% = 63
4. Egypt Otsu	350	7.3%	356X 7.3% = 26
5. Egyptian Chemicals and Drugs	250	5.2%	356X 5.2% = 19
Total	4783	100%	356X 100% = 356

Source: Personnel Department at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt, 2018

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents in the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt who participated in the survey. Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Job Title	Physicians	100	33%
	Nurses	150	50%
	Administrative Staff	50	17%
	Total	300	100%
2- Sex	Male	130	43%
	Female	170	57%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Single	125	42%
	Married	175	58%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Under 30	100	33%
	From 30 to 45	120	40%
	Above 45	80	27%
	Total	300	100%
5- Educational Level	University	210	70%
	Post Graduate	90	30%
	Total	300	100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	100	33%
	From 5 to 10	115	38%
	More than 10	85	29%
	Total	300	100%

7. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the significant role of EL in reducing CWB. A survey research method was used to collect data in this study. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to EL, CWB and biographical information of employees at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt. Data collection took approximately two months. About 357 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 84%.

8. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 36-item scale EL section is based on Brown et al., 2005. There were six items measuring fairness, six items measuring integrity, six items measuring role clarification, six items measuring power-sharing, six items measuring people orientation, and six items measuring ethical guidance.

The 21-item scale CWB section is based on Spector et al., 2006. There were four items measuring theft, four items measuring withdrawal, three items measuring sabotage, five items measuring kickbacks/corruption, and five items measuring misuse of time and resources.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

9. Methods of Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach’s Alpha, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) the statistical testing of hypotheses which includes F- test and T-test. They are found in SPSS.

9.1. Coding of Variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3): Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	Ethical Leadership	Fairness	6	Brown et al., 2005
		Integrity	6	
		Role Clarification	6	
		Power Sharing	6	
		People Orientation	6	
		Ethical Guidance	6	
Total EL			36	
Dependent Variable	Counterproductive Work Behavior	Theft	4	Spector et al., 2006
		Withdrawal	4	
		Sabotage	3	
		Kickbacks/Corruption	5	
		Misuse of Time and Resources	5	
Total CWB			21	

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out the means and standard deviations of EL and CWB.

Table (4) shows the mean and standard deviations of EL and CWB

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
EL	Fairness	3.41	0.982
	Integrity	3.55	0.967
	Role Clarification	3.57	0.964
	Power Sharing	3.42	0.890
	People Orientation	3.45	1.040
	Ethical Guidance	3.42	1.092
	Total Measurement	3.49	0.936
CWB	Theft	2.13	0.597
	Withdrawal	2.51	0.654
	Sabotage	1.78	0.719
	Kickbacks/Corruption	1.75	0.656
	Misuse of Time and Resources	1.77	0.639
	Total Measurement	2.03	0.590

Table (4) lists the mean and standard deviation among variables. The mean of each variable is more than 3, and this result indicates that the study subjects in general have a higher level of EL and CWB. The different facets of EL are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of fairness ($M=3.91$, $SD=0.982$). This was followed by integrity ($M=3.55$, $SD=0.967$), role clarification ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.964$), power-sharing ($M=3.42$, $SD=0.890$), people-orientation ($M=3.45$, $SD=1.04$), and ethical guidance ($M=3.42$, $SD=1.09$).

The different facets of CWB are examined. Most respondents identified the presence of theft ($M=2.13$, $SD=0.597$). This was followed by withdrawal ($M=2.51$, $SD=0.654$), sabotage ($M=1.78$, $SD=0.719$), kickbacks/corruption ($M=1.75$, $SD=0.656$), and misuse of time and resources ($M=1.77$, $SD=0.590$).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

ACC was used to evaluate the degree of internal consistency among the contents of the scale under testing. Table (5) shows the results of the reliability test for each variable of EL and CWB.

Table (5) Reliability of EL and CWB

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
EL	Fairness	6	0.844
	Integrity	6	0.832
	Role Clarification	6	0.821
	Power Sharing	6	0.760
	People Orientation	6	0.939
	Ethical Guidance	6	0.947
	Total Measurement	36	0.975
CWB	Theft	4	0.941
	Withdrawal	4	0.876
	Sabotage	3	0.795
	Kickbacks/Corruption	5	0.646
	Misuse of Time and Resources	5	0.610
	Total Measurement	21	0.939

The 24 items of EL are reliable because the ACC is 0.975. The six items of fairness scales are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.844. The integrity, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.832. The role clarification, which consists of six items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.821. The six items related to power-sharing are reliable as ACC is 0.760. Furthermore, the people-orientation which consists of six items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.939. Finally, the six items related to ethical guidance are reliable as ACC is 0.947.

The 28 items of CWB are reliable because the ACC is 0.939. The four items of theft are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.941. The withdrawal, which consists of four items, is reliable since the ACC is 0.876. The three items related to sabotage are reliable as ACC is 0.795. Furthermore, the kickbacks/corruption, which consists of five items, is reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.646. The five items of misuse of time and resources are reliable due to the fact that the ACC is 0.610.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (6) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix for all Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	EL	CWB
Ethical Leadership	3.49	0.936	1.000	
Counterproductive Work Behavior	2.04	0.590	0.259**	1.000

Table (6) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of a significant correlation between variables (EL and CWB).

The level of EL of employees is average (Mean=3.49; SD=0.936), while CWB is (Mean=2.04; SD= 0.590).

Table (6) reveals the existence of a positive correlation between EL and CWB (R=0.259; P < 0.01), which means that EL reduces CWB.

9.5. The Correlation between EL and CWB

Table (7): Correlation Matrix among EL and CWB

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Fairness	1						
Integrity	0.971**	1					
Role Clarification	0.950**	0.971**	1				
Power Sharing	0.952**	0.962**	0.951**	1			
People Orientation	0.780**	0.802**	0.801**	0.738**	1		
Ethical Guidance	0.812**	0.833**	0.836**	0.760**	0.980**	1	
Counterproductive Work Behavior	0.270**	0.267**	0.260**	0.222**	0.293**	0.353**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), the correlation between EL (Fairness) and CWB is 0.270. The correlation between EL (Integrity) and CWB is 0.267. For EL (Role Clarification) and CWB, the value is 0.260 whereas EL (Power Sharing) and CWB show a correlation value of 0.222. Also, the correlation between EL (People Orientation) and CWB is 0.293. Also, the correlation between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB is 0.353. The overall correlation between EL and CWB is 0.259.

9.6. Ethical Leadership (Fairness) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (Fairness) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

According to Table (8), the regression-coefficient between EL (Fairness) and CWB is R= 0.407 and R²= 0.166. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (Fairness). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because EL (Fairness) and CWB have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

Table (8) MRA Results for EL (Fairness) and CWB

The Variables of EL (Fairness)	Beta	R	R ²
1. The actions of managers are fair.	0.263**	0.036	0.001
2. My managers fulfill all that is committed to it.	0.084	0.284	0.080
3. Managers always take fair decisions.	0.099	0.106	0.011
4. My manager does not criticize me for no reason.	0.079	0.091	0.001
5. My manager seeks to achieve the interests of subordinates.	0.220	0.327	0.106
6. My manager is responsible for his actions.	0.368	0.337	0.113
▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC)		0.407	
▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF)		0.166	
▪ The Value of Calculated F		9.704	
▪ Degree of Freedom		6, 293	
▪ The Value of Indexed F		2.80	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
* P < 0.05 ** P < 0.01			

9.7. Ethical Leadership (Role Clarification) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:
There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (Role Clarification) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

Table (9) The Relationship between EL (Role Clarification) and CWB

The Variables of EL (Role Clarification)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My manager explains who is responsible and what.	0.267	0.036	0.001
2. My managers explain what work is expected of each employee.	0.129	0.284	0.080
3. Managers clarify the scope of responsibility of each member.	0.031	0.036	0.001
4. My manager explains the expected performance of each member.	0.029	0.083	0.006
5. My manager prioritizes work clearly.	0.233	0.327	0.106
6. My manager determines what performance is expected of each member.	0.409	0.337	0.113
▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC)		0.405	
▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF)		0.164	
▪ The Value of Calculated F		9.591	
▪ Degree of Freedom		6, 293	
▪ The Value of Indexed F		2.80	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
* P < 0.05			

According to Table (9), the regression-coefficient between EL (Role Clarification) and CWB is R= 0.405 and R²= 0.164. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (Role Clarification). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because EL (Role Clarification) and CWB have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

9.8. Ethical Leadership (Power Sharing) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:
There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (Power Sharing) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

Table (10) The Relationship between EL (Power Sharing) and CWB

The Variables of EL (Power Sharing)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My manager allows individuals to influence the decisions they make.	0.253**	0.036	0.001
2. My manager makes decisions in the light of recommendations made by employees.	0.115	0.284	0.080
3. My manager delegates responsibilities to subordinates.	0.013	0.069	0.004
4. My manager allows individuals to express an opinion on special decisions.	0.041	0.091	0.008
5. My manager listens to individuals' ideas when it comes to organization strategy.	0.084	0.058	0.003
6. My manager allows me to play a key role in setting my performance goals.	0.617**	0.337	0.113
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.405	0.164
		9.604	6, 293
		2.80	0.000
* P < 0.05 ** P < 0.01			

According to Table (10), the regression-coefficient between EL (Power Sharing) and CWB is R= 0.405 and R²= 0.164. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (Power Sharing). Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.9. Ethical Leadership (People Orientation) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:
There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (People Orientation) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

According to Table (11), the regression-coefficient between EL (People Orientation) and CWB is R= 0.432 and R²= 0.187. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (People Orientation). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because EL (People Orientation) and CWB have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

Table (11) The Relationship between EL (People Orientation) and CWB

The Variables of EL (People Orientation)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My manager is concerned with work problems.	0.152	0.328	0.107
2. Managers respect employees' concerns.	0.352	0.342	0.104
3. Managers provide the necessary support to employees in everything they need at work.	0.524	0.267	0.071
4. Managers assists in solving employees' personal problems.	0.404	0.280	0.078
5. Managers show great empathy for employees.	0.408**	0.036	0.001
6. Managers give sufficient time for personal contact with employees.	0.367**	0.284	0.080
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.432	0.187
		11.213	6, 293
		2.80	0.000
** P < 0.01			

9.10. Ethical Leadership (Ethical Guidance) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:
There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

Table (12) The Relationship between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB

The Variables of EL (Ethical Guidance)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Managers communicate with staff on ethical issues.	0.502	0.328	0.107
2. Managers clarify ethical issues.	0.394	0.342	0.116
3. Managers support ethical behavior.	0.387	0.267	0.071
4. Managers thanks the staff who act in accordance with ethical rules.	0.426	0.280	0.078
5. Managers reward employees who follow ethical rules.	0.161	0.327	0.106
6. Managers explain the possible consequences of ethical behavior.	0.184	0.337	0.113
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.437	0.191
		11.517	6, 293
		2.80	0.000
** P < 0.01			

According to Table (12), the regression-coefficient between EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB is R= 0.437 and R²= 0.191. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (Ethical Guidance). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because EL (Ethical Guidance) and CWB have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

9.11. Ethical Leadership (Integrity) and CWB

The relationship between EL and CWB is determined. The sixth hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no statistically significant relationship between EL (Integrity) and CWB at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt.

Table (13) The Relationship between EL (Integrity) and CWB

The Variables of EL (Integrity)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Managers do not seek to achieve their personal goals at the expense of others.	0.266	0.036	0.001
2. My managers do not hold me responsible for external problems for my control.	0.125	0.284	0.080
3. My managers keep their promises.	0.005	0.036	0.004
4. My manager does not hold me responsible for mistakes that I did not cause.	0.004	0.091	0.008
5. The manager's reaction to work is relatively predictable.	0.230	0.327	0.106
6. My managers always act in line with their words.	0.392	0.337	0.113
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients (MCC) ▪ Determination of Coefficient (DF) ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.403	0.162
		9.472	6, 293
		2.80	0.000
** P < 0.01			

According to Table (13), the regression-coefficient between EL (Integrity) and CWB is R= 0.403 and R²= 0.162. This means that the CWB can be explained by the dimensions of EL (Integrity). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because EL (Integrity) and CWB have a statistical relationship at the significance level of 0.01.

10. Research Results

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the hypotheses of the research, the study reached a set of results as follows:

1. The results support the view that EL (fairness, integrity, role clarification, power-sharing, people-orientation, and ethical guidance) is related to CWB (theft, withdrawal, sabotage, kickbacks/corruption, and misuse of time and resources at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt).

2. The relationship between EL and CWB in the organization is presented. The palliative role that EL can play in this relationship has been identified. In addition, the researcher did not monitor in this regard any study both in the Arab business environment in general, and Egypt in particular.
3. The present study emphasized the inverse relationship between EL and CWB in the organization. This requires the need for the advancement of educational and religious institutions to try to improve the ethics of leadership in general and work ethics in particular. This is part of their roles, as it goes beyond business organizations to influence the development process within the country.
4. The study found that the most influential dimensions of EL in CWB are, respectively, ethical orientation, individual orientation, fairness, integrity, role clarification, and power-sharing.
5. The present study emphasized the relationship between EL and CWB within the organization. This requires the need to develop the principle of self-control among employees in the organization. The development of work love and the spirit of the loyalty of employees in order to reduce the CWB within the organization.

11. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations summarized as follows:

1. Managers at Pharmaceutical industrial companies in Egypt can help their employees, through training interventions, to develop their EL.
2. Embodying the principles of EL of administrative leaders to be more immersed in organizational culture and pivotal to be a feature of organizational culture, and as a basis in the success of its implementation, because the performance of the work directly reflects the values, beliefs and customs of workers.
3. The need to pay attention to the mechanisms of social exchange through which to increase the impact of EL on the engagement of work and emotional commitment, in addition to the importance of the perception of workers that their moral leader represents the organization
4. Raising awareness and interest in the development of EL practices of leaders by subjecting them to training courses in this field, because of its positive impact on the development of positive behaviors of employees.
5. The need to develop relations of social exchange between leaders and subordinates in the organizations, and attention to the development of moral climate, and the behavior of EL. This is done through the development of an integrity-based code of ethics for both leaders and staff.
6. Developing trust relationships between the leader and the followers, determining the importance of the identity of the leader and the extent of his representation of the organization, and communicating the idea that the moral leader is a role model or model to be followed. This leads to increasing the desired organizational outputs, which is to increase the engagement of workers to their work, and increase their organizational commitment.
7. It is increasing the awareness of administrative leaders about the dimensions of integrity, people-orientation, and power-sharing, because of its positive impact on the behavior of workers.
8. The need for organizations to pay attention to good human resources practices to increase the level of EL. They must carry out their responsibilities to ensure that the leader is ethical, good management practices, and is a representative of the organization. By strengthening these factors and in the presence of ethics, work will witness good transactions between the leader and the followers.
9. To increase the level of EL represented by the organization is to be an effective strategy to increase work engagement and increase the emotional commitment of subordinates.
10. The need to minimize unethical behavior. The leaders play an important and vital role in increasing positive outcomes for subordinates and minimizing unwanted negative practices. Organizations should create a successful ethical work environment,
11. The need to use reward and punishment to emphasize proper behavior by followers. These will conduct more ethical practices, as well as their interest and attachment to work. This increases their emotional

commitment to the organization, makes them more satisfied with the work, having less conflict with their colleagues.

12. The importance of providing some training, development and development programs for ethical leaders by attending external seminars and attending university programs. This provides administrative leadership with practical reality in order to train leaders on how to make ethical decisions and transfer this learned behavior to practice within the organization.
13. The need to resort to the method of assessment centers. It is a highly efficient means of strengthening some management practices, and can be used to identify the ability of individuals to lead, and develop their leadership skills. The employees will increase their commitment to work, and their organizational commitment in the presence of an ethical role model who represents the organization. They express their behaviors and objectives, who exchange good transactions and benefits with affiliates, treat them with respect, raise their motivation levels, improve their skills and provide support and support, moral climate and development.

12. Future Researches

1. Conducting studies and research on the relationship between the dimension of concern for sustainability as a dimension of EL and organizational citizenship behavior.
2. Conducting studies and research on the relationship between the dimension of concern for sustainability as a dimension of EL and organizational commitment.
3. Conducting studies and research regarding the relationship between organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior and study the impact of each on the other.
4. The possibility of conducting similar studies to test the relationships through which EL processes are conducted, and their correlation with behavioral outcomes in the presence of many other interactive variables, such as the ethics and values of the followers and their beliefs, the pattern of the followers' personality, as well as some other variables of the leaders themselves, such as the personality pattern. Leader, age and gender.
5. Conducting similar studies to test the relationship between EL and unethical behavior of subordinates through engagement as a mediator.
6. Identifying the views and perceptions of leaders about the ethical or immoral behavior of subordinates in different organizations.
7. Conducting a comparative study between the public and private sectors to identify the different mechanisms, processes, and circumstances in which EL influences subordinate behavior, the extent of differences in EL, the ethical climate, and their correlation with negative and positive behavioral outcomes between workers in the two sectors.

References

- Altman, B. A., & Akdere, M. (2008). Towards a theoretical model of performance inhibiting workplace dynamics. *Human Resource Development Review*, 7(4), PP. 408–423.
- Aronson, E. (2001). Integrating Leadership Styles and Ethical Perspectives. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 18, PP. 244-256.
- Ayoko, O. B., Callan, V. J., & Hartel, C. E. (2003). Workplace conflict, bullying and counterproductive behaviors. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 11(4), PP. 283–301.
- Baruch, Y. (2005). Bullying on the net: Adverse behavior on e-mail and its impact. *Information Management*, 42, PP. 361–371.
- Bashir, S. Nasir M. Qayyum S. and Bashir, A. (2012). Dimensionality of Counterproductive Work Behaviors in Public Sector Organizations of Pakistan, *Public Organization Review*, 12 (4), PP. 357–366
- Bennett, R.J. & Robinson, S.L. (2000). Development of measure of workplace deviance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85, PP.349-360.

- Beu, B. and Buckley, R. (2001). The Hypothesized Relationship between Accountability and Ethical Behavior, *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 34, No. 1, PP. 57-73.
- Bolin, A., & Heatherly, L. (2001). Predictors of employee deviance: The relationship between bad attitudes and bad behavior. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 15(3), PP.405–418.
- Brown, M. E. and Treviño, L. K. (2006). Ethical Leadership: A Review and Future Directions«, *Leadership Quarterly*, 17, PP. 595–616.
- Brown, M. E. and Treviño, L. K. (2014). Do Role Models Matter? An Investigation of Role Modeling as an Antecedent of Perceived Ethical Leadership«, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 122, PP. 587–598.
- Brown, M. E. Treviño; L. K. and Harrison, D. A. (2005). »Ethical Leadership: A Social Learning Perspective for Construct Development and Testing«, *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 97, PP.117– 134.
- Chen, P. Y., & Spector, P. E. (1992). Relationships of work stressors with aggression, withdrawal, theft and substance use: An exploratory study. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 65(3), PP. 177–184.
- Choi, S. B.; Ullah, S. M. and Kwak, W. J. (2015). »Ethical Leadership and Followers' Attitudes toward Corporate Social Responsibility: The Role of Perceived Ethical Work Climate«, *Social Behavior and Personality*, 43(3), PP. 353-366.
- Cortina, L. M., & Magley, V. J. (2003). Raising voice, risking retaliation: Events following interpersonal mistreatment in the workplace. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 8(4), PP. 247–265.
- Dajani, M. A. (2015). »The Impact of Employee Engagement on Job Performance and Organizational Commitment in the Egyptian Banking Sector«, *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 3(5), PP. 138-147.
- De Hoogh, A. H. B. & Den Hartog, D. N. (2008). »Ethical and Despotic Leadership, Relationships with Leader's Social Responsibility, Top Management Team Effectiveness and Subordinates' Optimism: A Multi-Method Study, *The Leadership Quarterly*, 19, PP. 297–311.
- De Hoogh, B. Den Hartog, N. (2009). Empowering behaviour and leader fairness and integrity: studying perceptions of ethical leader behaviour from a levels-of-analysis perspective, *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, Vol.18, No. 2, PP.199-230.
- De Hoogh, B. Den Hartog, N. (2009). Neuroticism and locus of control as moderators of the relationships of charismatic and autocratic leadership with burnout, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol 94 (4), PP. 1058-1067.
- Den Hartog, D. N. and Belschak, F. D. (2012). »Work Engagement and Machiavellianism in the Ethical Leadership Process«, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 107, PP. 35–47.
- Eisenbeiss, S. A. (2012). »Re-Thinking Ethical Leadership: An Interdisciplinary Integrative Approach«, *The Leadership Quarterly*, 23, PP. 791–808.
- Fox, S., Spector, P., & Miles, D. (2001). Counterproductive work behavior (CWB) in response to job stressors and organizational justice: Some mediator and moderator tests for autonomy and emotions. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 59, PP. 291–309.
- Fulmer, R. (2005). What leaders and their organizations can do to develop ethical leaders. In P. J. Doh & S. A. Stumpf (Eds.), *Handbook on responsible leadership and governance in global business*, Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, PP. 42- 53.
- Gabbidon, S. L., Patrick, P. A., & Peters, S. A. (2006). An empirical assessment of employee theft lawsuits involving allegations of employer misconduct. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 34, PP. 175–183.
- Giacalone, R. A., & Greenberg, J. (1997). *Antisocial behavior in organizations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Griffin, R. W., O'Leary-Kelly, A., & Collins, J. (1998). Dysfunctional work behaviors in organizations. *Trends in Organizational Behavior*, 5, PP. 65–82.
- Gruys, M., & Sackett, P. (2003). Investigating the dimensionality of counterproductive work behavior. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 11, PP. 30-42.

- Hollinger, R. C., & Clark, J. P. (1982). Formal and informal social controls of employee deviance. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 23(3), PP.333–343.
- Hollinger, R. C., & Clark, J. P. (1983). Deterrence in the workplace: Perceived certainty, perceived severity, and employee theft. *The University of North Carolina Press*, 62(2), PP. 398–418.
- Hollinger, R.C., and Clark, J.P. (1982) Formal and informal social controls of employee deviance. *The Sociology Quarterly*, 23, PP. 333-343.
- Khuong, M. N., and Dung, D. T. (2015). »The Effect of Ethical Leadership and Organizational Justice on Employee Engagement — the Mediating Role of Employee Trust«. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 6(4), PP. 235-240.
- Kulas, J. T., McInnerney, J. E., Demuth, R. F., & Jadwinski, V. (2007). Employee satisfaction and theft: Testing climate perceptions as a mediator. *The Journal of Psychology*, 141(4), PP. 389–402.
- Lipman, M., & McGraw, W. R. (1988). Employee theft: A \$40 billion industry. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 498, PP. 51–59.
- Mahembe, B. and Engelbrecht, A.S. (2013). »A Confirmatory Factor Analytical Study of a Servant Leadership Measure in South Africa, *Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 39 (2), PP. 1127-1135.
- Marcus, B., & Schuler, H. (2004). Antecedents of counterproductive behavior at work: A general perspective. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(4), PP. 647–660.
- Monks, C. P., Smith, P. K., Naylor, P., Barter, C., Ireland, J. L., & Coyne, I. (2009). Bullying in different contexts: Commonalities, differences and the role of theory. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 14, PP. 146–156.
- Motowidlo, S. J., & Schmit, M. J. (1999). Performance assessment in unique jobs. In D. R. Ilgen & E. D. Pulakos (Eds.), *The changing nature of performance*, San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, PP. 56-86
- Neves, P. and Story, J. (2015). Ethical Leadership and Reputation: Combined Indirect Effects on Organizational Deviance«, *Journal of Business Ethics*, 127, PP. 165–176.
- Niehoff, B. P., & Paul, R. J. (2000). Causes of employee theft and strategies that HR managers can use for prevention. *Human Resource Management*, 39(1), PP. 51–64.
- Ones, D. S. (2002). Introduction to the special issue on counterproductive behaviors at work. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 10, PP. 1–4.
- Organ, D. (1990). The motivational basis of organizational citizenship behavior, *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 12, PP. 43-72.
- Palanski, M. and Yammarino, F. (2009). Integrity and Leadership: A Multi-Level Conceptual Framework, *The Leadership Quarterly* 20(3), PP. 405-420
- Peterson, D. (2002). Deviant workplace behavior and the organization's ethical climate. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 17, PP. 47-61.
- Porath, C. L., & Erez, A. (2009). Overlooked but not untouched: How rudeness reduces onlookers' performance on routine and creative tasks. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 109, PP. 29–44.
- Raelin, J. A. (1994). Three scales of professional deviance within organizations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 15, PP.483-501.
- Resick, C. Hanges, P. Dickson, M. and Mitchelson, J. (2006). A Cross-Cultural Examination of the Endorsement of Ethical Leadership, *Journal of Business Ethics* 63 (4), PP. 345-359.
- Robinson, S. L., & Bennett, R. J. (1995). A typology of deviant workplace behaviors: A multidimensional scaling study. *Academy of Management Journal*, 38, PP. 555–572.
- Rotundo, M., & Sackett, P. (2002). The relative importance of task, citizenship, and counterproductive performance to global ratings of job performance: a policy-capturing approach. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87, PP. 66-80.
- Saucer, Jr. W. I. (2007). Employee theft: Who, how, why, and what can be done. *Sam Advanced Management Journal*, PP. 13–25.
- Saunders, P., Huynh, A., & Delahunty, J. G. (2007). Defining workplace bullying behavior professional lay definitions of workplace bullying. *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry*, 30, PP. 340–354.

- Schmidtke, J. M. (2007). The relationship between social norms consensus perceived similarity and observers reactions to coworkers theft. *Human Resource Management*, 46(4), PP. 561–582.
- Spector, P. E., Fox, S., Penney, L. M., Bruursema, K., Goh, A., & Kessler, S. (2006). The dimensionality of counterproductivity: Are all counterproductive behaviors created equal? *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68, PP. 446–460.
- Stouten, J.; Van Dijke, M. and De Cremer, D. (2012). Ethical leadership: An Overview and Future Perspectives«, *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 11, PP. 1–6.
- Trevino, L. K. and Nelson, A. K. (2011). *Managing Business Ethics: Straight Talk about how to do it Right*«, Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.
- Trevino, L. K., & Brown, M. E. (2005). Managing to be ethical: Debunking five business ethics myths. *Strategic human resource management: theory and practice*.
- Trevino, L. K., Brown, M., & Hartman, L. P. (2003). A qualitative investigation of perceived executive ethical leadership: Perceptions from inside and outside the executive suite. *Human Relations*, 56(1), 5.
- Tucker, J. (1993). Everyday forms of employee resistance. *Sociological Forum*, 8(1).
- Vickers, M. H. (2001). Bullying as unacknowledged organizational evil: A researcher's story. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 13(4), PP. 205–217.
- Weatherbee, T. G. (2010). Counterproductive use of technology at work: Information & communications technologies and cyber deviancy. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20, PP. 35–44.
- Yukl, G. (2006). *Leadership in organizations*, 6th edition. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Zhu, W., May, D. R., & Avolio, B. J. (2004). The impact of ethical leadership behavior on employee outcomes: The roles of psychological empowerment and authenticity. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 11(1), PP. 16-26.